

Implementation of Islamic Education Values in Notary Families in Palu City Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: This study discusses the Implementation of the values of Islamic Education in the Palu City Notary family. This study used is a qualitative method with data gathering using field observational, in-depth interviews, and written material analysis. The data was then analyzed using inductive, dedicated and comparative analysis. The results of the study revealed that the Muslim Notary families in Palu City understands and implements of Islamic education values. Muslim notary families apply and practice the values of Islamic education include the values of Aqidah and Morals. Islamic values are implemented in their professional life and in their families. The result of Islamic education and values implementation are reflected in feeling of fear to Allah which means to have feelings in the heart of Allah. The person who fears Allah the most is the person who knows and realizes himself the most. Continuous training is needed to increase listening to religious advice originating from the Al-Qur'an and Hadith. Hoping to Allah that all the good deeds that we are about to do will receive the pleasure of Allah and be accepted as a pious child and Allah will forgive sins. By hoping in Allah, humans are required to try to increase their faith and increase good deeds both to Allah and fellow human beings. 6). Praying too much for forgiveness so that the sins that have already been done will receive forgiveness from Allah SWT.

KEYWORDS: Education values, Islamic values, Islamic education, notary family, Indonesia

INTRODUCTION

Islamic education, known as 'Al-Bait al-Madrasah al-Uu laa' (home is the first school), is where children acquire Islamic education before receiving formal or non-formal education outside the home (Makmur, Nurdin, & Pettalongi, 2022; Palinge, Nurdin, & Rusdin, 2022). Children become familiar with the household environment, including its contents and situations. Family education plays a role in this process, with parents as natural educators. Within the family, blood ties create intimate relationships based on sincere affection. It is the primary factor for parents in guiding their immature children within their respective families.

In the family environment, the roles of the mother and father determine whether a child will remain true to their innate disposition or deviate from it (Pratama, Pettalongi, & Nurdin, 2022; Rahmawati, Nurdin, & Pettalongi, 2022). No child is born with a particular religion; the parents make them Jewish, Christian, Zoroastrian, or followers of another religion. A child born into a Muslim family tends to become a Muslim, just as a child born into a non-Muslim family tends to adopt their parents' religion. Hence, the innate disposition of the child must be preserved.

The harmony within the family dramatically influences a child's education (Hess & Camara, 1979). Children observe the relationship between their parents, evaluate their behaviors, and absorb both the positive and negative aspects of the family environment. If there is a shift in values due to disharmony, the parents' behavior becomes incomprehensible to the child. What they see creates a dilemma in their perception. The core values of education within the family that need attention include respect and obedience towards parents and the physical and spiritual well-being of all family members. Another core values of education also include loyalty, solidarity, and pure cooperation among all family members (Halgunseth, Ispa, & Rudy, 2006).

Understanding education, particularly Islamic education, means pedagogically analyzing a primary aspect of the divine mission bestowed upon humanity through Prophet Muhammad (Sahin, 2013). As divine guidance, Islam carries pedagogical implications that can guide individuals to become true believers, virtuous Muslims, and pious individuals through a gradual process. Islam's teachings (doctrines) encompass the value system that consistently shapes the course of Islamic education, adapting to society's needs and progress over time.

Attitude is the initial stage that explains why children often fail to appreciate the established values within their families (Nurdin, Nurliana, & Mashuri, 2022; Taraju, Nurdin, & Pettalongi, 2022). Thus, the author emphasizes the importance of various Islamic educational values in the family environment. Indonesia is predominantly a Muslim nation built upon Islamic values. Building an Islamic community is difficult but requires a lengthy process, starting with individuals, families, and society. Once each group understands this process, it will contribute to the best community of Muslims. "You are the best nation produced for mankind. You enjoin what is right and forbid what is wrong." (Quran 3:110)

Family represents a miniature "small state" that symbolizes unity, peace, goodness, happiness, and tranquility felt by all its members. However, it does not mean that disturbances or deviations from the family structure cannot occur. For example, financial difficulties, disharmony leading to divorce, criminal activities, deviations, and so on pose threats and create crises within the family structure. Therefore, in navigating society at large, physical and psychological strength is required.

In the modern era, due to the influence of globalization, the general goals of education and the specific goals of family education have been impacted by moral clashes affecting children. They have become less familiar with Eastern cultures, which are rich in noble values, including religious and cultural values (Nurdin, 2023). Islamic rules are not restrictive but somewhat conciliatory, aiming to reconcile conflicting interests. In this context, the rules are known as *fiqh*. *Fiqh* is a legal system that governs the lives of individuals, especially Muslims, in all aspects of life, including personal, family, social, and political spheres.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Values of Islamic Education

In daily life, values are something precious, of high quality, and indicate highly beneficial rates to all humans (Poetz & Schreier, 2012). In this context, values are based on morality. Values are the essence of something that makes it worthwhile and justifiable for humans to strive for. According to Bertens, values are everything that attracts humans, something they seek, something that brings them joy, something they like. In essence, values and feelings are inseparable. Feelings are psychological activities where individuals experience existing values. It implies that everything holds value for someone, whether it evokes positive or negative feelings.

Values are the essence attached to something significant in human life, particularly in relation to goodness and acts of goodness. Values refer to characteristics or things that are important or useful for humanity (Naseer, Donia, Syed, & Bashir, 2020). Values are abstract, ideal concepts. They are not tangible objects, not facts. They involve not only matters of right and wrong that demand empirical proof but also the social understanding, liking, or disliking of values.

Based on experts' opinions mentioned above, values are the essence attached to something significant in human life. The sense is only meaningful once humans need it, but it doesn't mean the soul exists because humans need it. However, the meaningfulness of the essence increases according to the capacity of human understanding. Therefore, values are something that humans prioritize, concerning everything as either good or bad, as abstractions, perspectives, or intentions derived from various experiences with strict behavioral selection.

Something is considered valuable when an individual's level of understanding reaches the point where the value holds meaning for them. Thus, something may have value for one person but not for another because values are crucial in this life, and there is an essential relationship between the subject and the object (Barth, Godemann, Rieckmann, & Stoltenberg, 2007). Values serve as driving forces in life, giving meaning and validation to one's actions. Values have both intellectual and emotional aspects. The combination of these two dimensions determines the value and function of something in life. When the dynamic element is minimal, and the intellectual factor is dominant in attributing meaning and validation to action, it is referred to as norms or principles, such as faith, justice, brotherhood, and so on. These norms become values when implemented in a group's behavior and thinking patterns. Norms are universal and absolute, while values are specific and relative to each group (Wahyuddin, Nurdin, & Pettalongi, 2022).

Education is undoubtedly the most crucial aspect of human life. It is highly strategic in shaping culture and civilization because of its strategic role in human life (Plucker, Beghetto, & Dow, 2004). Thus, it is improbable that the Quran does not provide information on how humans can cultivate culture and society. When discussing education, it is impossible to separate it from the essence of education itself. The nature of education is to guide and assist individuals toward maturity.

METHODOLOGY

This study uses qualitative methods. In qualitative research, the use of theory is only a guide so that the research focus is in accordance with the facts in the field (Nurdin & Pettalongi, 2022; Nurdin, Stockdale, & Scheepers, 2016). The data was collected through direct observation, in-depth interview, and written document analysis in the research site (Rusli, Hasyim, & Nurdin, 2021; Rusli & Nurdin, 2022). In other words, the implementation of Islamic education values in notary families can be easily understood through close engagement with the notary families' members during direct observation and in-depth interviews with them. The data was analyzed using thematic analysis from Corbin and Strauss (2003). The analysis was started from open coding, axial coding, and selective coding. The final results of the data analysis is themes found from the data. The location of this research is in Palu city located in Central Sulawesi Indonesia. Due to notary families in Palu is limited, then we took all of them for the subject of this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Implementation of Islamic Education Values in Notary Families

In every profession, especially those accompanied by special powers, such as Notaries who deal with individual or public interests, heavy responsibilities are entrusted legally and morally. It is understandable that a Notary, despite possessing professional skills in the legal field. A Notary will only be able to fulfill the responsibilities and morals with a deep understanding of the dignity and duties of their position, as well as the values and ethical standards. Therefore, they cannot be expected to fulfill their duties as required by law and the interests of the general public.

These requirements are demanded not only by law but also based on the trust bestowed upon them by the legislation, as seen in the position of a Notary. The position held by a Notary is one of trust, and it is because of this trust that individuals are willing to entrust something to them, which in turn carries a heavy responsibility.

A Notary must be accountable and uphold legal ethics, dignity, and the nobility of their position. In addition to high professional responsibility and ethics, good integrity and moral values are important prerequisites that every Notary must possess. It is because professional responsibility and ethics have a close relationship with integrity and morals. With good integrity and moral values, it is possible to expect a Notary to demonstrate high professional responsibility and ethics, as professional responsibility and ethics must be based on good integrity and morals, just as theoretical and technical skills are in the notarial profession.

Only when a Notary meets the above requirements can they be expected to fulfill their duties well, in accordance with legal needs and the interests of society. To better understand the role of a Notary in society, it is deemed necessary first to understand the history of the Notary institution.

The practice of a Notary, which arises from the surface, is to articulate the desires and objectives of clients. In a deed, as a public official and Indonesian citizen, you are aware of your devotion to only One God and perform your duties in accordance with Pancasila, being conscious and obedient to the law. Regulations govern notaries and should use the proper Indonesian language.

In carrying out their duties, notaries are aware of their obligation to work independently, honestly, impartially, and with a sense of responsibility. Notaries perform their duties in one designated office in accordance with the law and do not establish branch offices or representative offices or even use intermediaries. Furthermore, it is expected that Notaries carry out their duties professionally, sincerely caring for and defending the honor and reputation of Notaries/Notarial Corps, supporting each other constructively, and reminding one another. It is the foundation for complying with the ethical code of conduct.

B. Islamic Perspective on the Notary Profession

The Islamic perspective on the Notary profession is that it is a form of worship to seek halal sustenance. In terms of the Notary profession, Islam teaches us to carry out our tasks and duties in everyday life by assisting those in need of services, especially in the field of notarial work, while prioritizing good behavior, honesty, fairness, and impartiality. The Notary profession can provide better legal certainty, particularly regarding the rights and obligations of individuals. For the people in the City of Palu, it is important to gain knowledge and consider Notaries as partners who can serve as a source of information for legal issues encountered in daily life.

"Islam has fundamental values in education: faith, worship, and moral values. These values are derived from the Quran and Hadith, and Muslim society must implement these fundamental values as part of their submission to Allah SWT."

The Islamic educational values of fairness, honesty, and discipline are essential in the Notary profession as mediators who validate agreements between two parties. The Islamic educational values applied to Notary families include following the commands of Allah SWT and avoiding His prohibitions, practicing courtesy, and maintaining the trust placed upon them. Based on the interview results above, the researcher emphasizes that faith, worship, and moral values are crucial for a Notary to fulfill their duties. When carrying out their tasks, a Notary must have faith or submission to Allah SWT, sincerely believe, obey the commands, refrain from prohibitions, and adhere to the faithful and straight path of faith, which involves the belief in the oneness of Allah SWT.

Islam calls upon humanity to believe and have faith in the oneness of God, and humans must submit themselves. Regarding worship values and moral values, faith is the foundation of morality. Faith can create self-awareness for individuals to adhere to moral norms and noble values firmly. One of the functions of morality is explained in the Hadith of Prophet Muhammad (SAW): "Innama bi'istu liutammima makarimal Akhlaq." (Meaning: I have been sent to the perfect noble character) Perfecting character becomes meaningful when placed within the framework of shaping an ethical society. Therefore, religion encourages individuals to have noble character. Religion considers morality as the completion of its teachings because religion comprises belief (Aqidah) and behavior.

Character reflects behavior. The Notary profession is essential as a mediator and validator of agreements between two parties. The Islamic educational values applied to Notary families include following the commands of Allah SWT, avoiding prohibitions, practicing courtesy, and maintaining the trust placed upon them.

C. Strategies for Implementing Islamic Values in Notary Families

Implementing Islamic educational values in Notary families in the City of Palu can be seen in the faith of a Notary, a firm conviction justified by faith and manifested through actions. According to interviews conducted by the author and researcher, it has been observed that of approximately 20 Notaries in Palu, around 15 individuals genuinely have faith. In contrast, others have faith but to a lesser extent due to their youth and limited knowledge of morals and beliefs.

Typically, individuals who have yet to receive guidance from Allah or are less inclined to introspect and evaluate their actions, especially those who have not consistently performed worship to their Lord, can be considered lacking the fear of Allah SWT. Achieving that requires continuous training, such as listening to religious lectures based on the Quran and Hadith of Prophet Muhammad SAW. Examples of moral conduct include practicing gratitude, patience, humility, forgiveness, relying on Allah, and showing kindness to parents.

For the people in the city of Palu to increase their knowledge and consider Notaries as working partners, especially for those who are unfamiliar with the law, it is important to entrust legal actions such as agreements, contracts, and property transfers to a Notary, who is a public official charged with the task of creating legal documents. Upholding trust in performing their duties by adhering to legal regulations ensures that people feel secure and their rights are protected when using Notary services. Applying Islamic educational values is crucial in the role of a Notary, as Islam teaches us to respect and value one another.

Holding trust while carrying out duties by constantly adhering to legal provisions is crucial for Notaries. They operate within the boundaries of the law, creating a sense of security and ensuring the protection of rights when people utilize the services of a Notary. Implementing Islamic educational values as a Notary is highly significant, as Islam teaches us to respect and value one another.

A strong sense of togetherness is deeply felt regarding Islamic educational values among Notary families. They uphold the bonds of kinship, engage in social activities, and assist needy individuals. For example, when a Notary family experiences a loss in Palu City or Sigi Regency, everyone in Palu City comes together to support and provide contributions determined by the family. Similarly, during the 2018 earthquake and tsunami, The researcher personally received assistance from the Indonesian Notary Association to repair our destroyed house. Overall, the average aid reached various areas in Central Sulawesi, including Palu City, Sigi Regency, Donggala Regency, and Parigi Moutong Regency, provided by the INI headquarters in Jakarta.

The role of a Notary is vital, particularly when individuals require bank loans. Notaries play a significant role in facilitating the signing of credit agreements at banks. Without a Notary, the loan cannot be granted. Banks rely on Notaries for credit agreements and the creation of mortgage deeds, as the certificates need to be legally bound to the loan and registered with the Land Office in Palu City.

When conveying legal counseling, particularly in notarial matters, a Notary records and understands clients' needs to ensure validity. Islam teaches us to be fair and base our actions on faith and moral values derived from the Al-Qu'ran and Hadith. Therefore, these principles must be implemented daily and while performing Notarial duties.

"The Notary profession is important as a mediator that validates agreements between two parties. Applying Islamic educational values in carrying out Notarial duties is crucial because Islam teaches us to respect and value one another."

Verse 4:58 of Surah An-Nisa states: "Indeed, Allah commands you to render trusts to whom they are due and when you judge between people to judge with justice. Excellent is that which Allah instructs you. Indeed, Allah is ever Hearing and Seeing." This verse emphasizes the obligation to judge fairly when making decisions among people. It is highly relevant to the Notary's duty of remaining impartial while performing tasks. A Notary's role must be characterized by fairness, as it is a form of worship, fulfilling Allah SWT commands and avoiding prohibited actions. Notaries should refrain from being biased or leading others astray and must adhere to regulations, codes of ethics, and Notarial practices.

One of the informants stated the following:

"Personally and professionally, Islamic educational values are applied in the Notary profession through mutual respect, valuing others' rights, acting fairly toward clients without favoritism, maintaining the confidentiality and trustworthiness of created deeds, and ensuring that the deeds are halal."

Based on the above interviews, the researcher affirms that, in carrying out the tasks assigned by clients, a Notary cannot take sides in transactions such as agreements. They must be honest and impartial, safeguarding the confidentiality of deed contents. Notaries should refrain from creating deeds related to unlawful activities or including agreements that contradict the provisions of the Civil Code, as stated in Article 1330 of the Constitution.

Islamic teachings serve as a solid and perfect foundation for life. Long before the existence of the Notary profession, Islam had already regulated matters in the Al-Qur'an regarding the need for recording agreements, the use of witnesses, and matters of gift-giving, among others. Another informant explained:

"In the Islamic perspective, a Notary must not favor anyone and is obliged to maintain trust and confidentiality regarding Notarial deeds, as the Notary profession is based on trust."

Based on the interviews above, the researcher affirms that the Notary must stand among the parties involved regarding Notarial tasks. When drafting agreements, the Notary should seek input from both parties to reach a mutual agreement reflected in the deed. If the act only reflects the interests of one party, it becomes disadvantageous. Therefore, the Notary must carefully select and arrange words to prevent harm to either party. A disagreement may lead to a breach of contract, which will subsequently become a legal issue. Hence, before signing the Notarial deed, the Notary must read the contents aloud. If both parties agree, the act is signed and documented (photographed) as irrefutable evidence.

Notaries must provide legal counseling and pro bono legal assistance to the community, especially those less fortunate. Another informant stated:

"According to us, the current Notary profession greatly contributes to the development of Islam, both in theory and practice. For example, matters of inheritance are handled with certainty. Notaries faithfully execute their tasks and authorities by implementing Islamic values regulated by the Notary's Code of Ethics. It promotes good relations among the community and fellow Notaries."

Based on the above interviews, the researcher emphasizes that while the Notary's opinion regarding Islamic values is commendable, the Notary has yet to be able to explain the actual implementation of these values. Their perspective seems limited to worship matters, such as praying together with staff and family, following religious obligations, and promoting tolerance. It is important to

note that each Notary may have different viewpoints, and not all Notaries fully understand the values of Islamic education, even if they are Muslims. The Notary's opinion needs to provide specific guidance on the implementation and execution of Islamic educational values, considering the various aspects involved.

CONCLUSION

The profession of a Notary in Islam has been explicitly regulated in Surah Al-Baqarah, verse 282, which means: "O you who have believed, when you contract a debt for a specified term, write it down. And let a scribe write [it] between you in justice. Let no scribe refuse to write as Allah has taught him. So let him write, let the one who owes the debt dictate, and let him fear Allah, his Lord, and not leave anything out of it. But if the one who owes the obligation is of limited understanding or weak or unable to dictate himself, then let his guardian dictate justice. And bring to witness two witnesses from among your men. And if there are not two men [available], then a man and two women from those you accept as witnesses - so that if one of the women errs, the other can remind her.

Please do not refuse the testimony of witnesses when they are called upon, and do not be weary of writing it, whether small or large, for its specified term. That is more just in the sight of Allah, stronger as evidence, and more likely to prevent doubt except when you conduct an immediate transaction among yourselves. Then there is no blame upon you if you do not write it. And take witnesses when you conclude a contract. Let no harm befall the scribe or the witness. For if you do so, it is indeed a grave disobedience. And fear Allah. Allah teaches you, and Allah knows of all things. The profession of a Notary has existed since the 7th century CE, long before the civil law."

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